

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND WORK LIFE BALANCE AMONG NURSES OF LADOKE AKINTOLA TEACHING HOSPITAL OSOGBO, OSUN STATE NIGERIA

Oguntamu Titilayo Ramota

Department Of Psychology, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, Osun State

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*Emotional
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Abstract: *This study examined emotional intelligence and work-life balance among nurses of Ladoke Akintola teaching hospital Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study while one null hypothesis was formulated. This study adopted a descriptive correlational survey research design. The target population for this study comprised 250 senior nursing personnel, including Directors of Nursing Services, Deputy and Assistant Directors, Chief and Assistant Nurse Tutors, and Principals of Nursing at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State. A sample of 105 participants was drawn using simple random sampling technique. Data for this study were collected through a structured questionnaire. The instrument consisted of three sections: Section A elicited demographic information of the respondents, Section B contained standardized items adapted from the Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS) to assess the level of emotional intelligence, while Section C adopted the Work-Life Balance Scale by Hayman (2005) to measure work-life balance among the nurses. Research Questions 1 and 2 were answered using descriptive statistics such as mean scores, and standard deviation. Research Question 3 was analyzed using inferential statistics of regression analysis. All hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. The findings revealed that nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital demonstrated a high level of emotional intelligence and a moderate level of work-life balance. It was also found out that emotional intelligence is a strong positive and significant predictor of work-life balance among nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State. It was recommended that hospital management should sustain and further strengthen emotional intelligence competencies among nurses through regular professional development programmes, emotional wellness workshops, communication training, and stress-management seminars.*

Oguntamu Titilayo Ramota

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Introduction

The healthcare system remains one of the most demanding service sectors globally, with nursing professionals occupying a central position in the delivery of quality patient care. Nursing is widely acknowledged as a demanding profession that requires not only technical competence but also strong emotional regulation, empathy, and resilience. In Nigeria, the healthcare system is characterized by heavy patient loads, inadequate staffing, and extended working hours, all of which place considerable strain on nurses' psychological and physical well-being. Studies have shown that nurses frequently experience occupational stress arising from excessive workload, emotional exposure to suffering patients, and limited institutional support systems, which collectively influence their quality of work life and personal balance between professional and family responsibilities (Akinwale, Omishakin, Abokede, Ajewole, Akinbowale & Adeniyi, 2024; Sende, Anayo & Ebizie, 2026).

At Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, nurses function in a tertiary healthcare environment where the demand for healthcare services often exceeds available human and material resources. This imbalance intensifies job pressure and creates conditions where emotional fatigue becomes common. A study conducted within the same institutional environment revealed that nurses often experience high levels of work-related

stress due to excessive workload, emotional exposure to dying patients, and uncertainty in patient care outcomes (Akinwale, Edegwa & Ofuani, 2024). Despite these challenges, many nurses still demonstrate strong caring behaviour, suggesting that internal psychological resources such as emotional intelligence may play a critical role in sustaining professional performance even under stressful conditions.

Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to perceive, understand, regulate, and manage emotions in oneself and others. Within the nursing profession, emotional intelligence is particularly important because nurses are required to interact continuously with patients, families, and multidisciplinary teams under emotionally charged conditions. Ben, Okemini, Eguchi and Ude (2026) stressed that emotionally intelligent nurses are better equipped to manage workplace stress, maintain empathy in patient care, and sustain positive interpersonal relationships in clinical settings. This emotional competence helps reduce burnout and enhances resilience, thereby supporting better adjustment to demanding work environments.

Work-life balance, on the other hand, reflects the degree to which individuals are able to effectively manage competing demands from work and personal life without experiencing excessive role conflict. Among nurses, achieving work-life balance is often challenging due to

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shift rotations, emergency duties, and overtime schedules (Ben, et al., 2026). According to Akinawo and Onisile (2019) poor work-life balance among nurses is associated with increased psychological distress, reduced job satisfaction, and impaired mental health outcomes. When nurses are unable to balance work and personal life effectively, it often leads to emotional exhaustion, reduced productivity, and strained family relationships.

The interaction between emotional intelligence and work-life balance is therefore critical in explaining nurses' well-being and performance outcomes. Emotional intelligence provides nurses with the psychological tools needed to regulate stress and maintain emotional stability, which in turn supports healthier work-life integration. For instance, nurses with high emotional intelligence are more likely to engage in adaptive coping strategies such as positive reframing, emotional regulation, and effective communication, which reduce the spillover of work stress into their personal lives. Conversely, low emotional intelligence may result in emotional exhaustion, poor boundary management, and difficulty in separating work responsibilities from personal life demands.

Recent empirical studies within the Nigerian healthcare sector have continued to show that emotional intelligence plays a significant role in how nurses cope with occupational demands and maintain psychological stability. In tertiary hospitals, nurses are frequently exposed to emotionally draining situations involving critically ill patients, emergency responses, and prolonged interactions with distressed families. Within this context, emotionally intelligent

nurses tend to demonstrate stronger coping capacity, emotional control, and interpersonal effectiveness. Akinwale, Omishakin, Abokede, Ajewole, Akinbowale and Adeniyi (2024) observed that despite high workplace stress among nurses in Osogbo, many still maintained positive caring behaviour, suggesting the presence of internal emotional adjustment mechanisms. Similarly, Sani, Jafaru, Ashipala and Sahabi (2024) reported that unmanaged occupational stress among nurses negatively affected patient safety culture and reduced psychological efficiency in clinical practice. In another related study, Onisile, Olanipekun, Akintayo and Okafor (2024) found that nurses who adopted adaptive coping approaches such as emotional regulation and relaxation techniques demonstrated better resilience under stressful working conditions.

Beyond emotional regulation in clinical practice, researchers have increasingly linked emotional intelligence with work-life balance among healthcare professionals in Nigeria. Work-life balance has become a growing concern because nurses often combine demanding shift schedules with family obligations and personal responsibilities. According to Akinwale, et al (2024), excessive workload, poor organizational support, and unhealthy work environments significantly undermine the quality of work-life among nurses and other healthcare workers in government hospitals. Relatedly, Dominic, Muritala, Wetsi and Gambo (2024) explained that persistent workplace stress contributes to fatigue, emotional exhaustion, and reduced productivity among nurses in Nigerian public hospitals. Ayantunde, Afolabi and Oderinde

(2025) further noted that prolonged exposure to job stress in hospital environments contributes to exhaustion and diminished psychological well-being among nurses. These studies imply that emotional intelligence may influence how effectively nurses manage competing professional and personal demands. Nurses with stronger emotional awareness and self-regulation abilities are more likely to maintain healthier boundaries between work and personal life, thereby reducing emotional spillover from the workplace into family and social domains.

Although previous studies have examined workplace stress, coping strategies, and quality of work-life among nurses in Nigeria, there remains limited empirical attention on the direct relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance, particularly among nurses in tertiary healthcare institutions in Osun State. Most available studies have focused largely on stress prevalence, job performance, patient safety, or coping mechanisms without specifically investigating how emotional intelligence contributes to balancing professional and personal responsibilities among nurses. For instance, Akinwale et al. (2024) concentrated on work-related stress and quality of life, while Onisile et al. (2024) examined stress and coping strategies among clinical nurses in Osogbo. Similarly, Sani et al. (2024) emphasized patient safety culture rather than the broader issue of work-life integration. Consequently, there is still insufficient evidence explaining whether emotional intelligence significantly predicts work-life balance among nurses working within

demanding tertiary hospital settings such as Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo. This background therefore informed this study.

Statement of the Problem

Nurses in public teaching hospitals are increasingly confronted with heavy workloads, shift rotations, prolonged working hours, emotional exposure to critically ill patients, inadequate staffing, and rising healthcare demands. At Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, these workplace pressures may negatively affect nurses' ability to effectively manage emotions and maintain balance between work obligations and personal life responsibilities. Reports from previous studies conducted among nurses in similar hospital settings in Nigeria indicate persistent experiences of occupational stress, emotional exhaustion, fatigue, and reduced quality of work-life arising from demanding work conditions. In many cases, nurses struggle to separate workplace stress from family and social life, thereby creating emotional spillover that affects both professional efficiency and personal well-being.

The persistence of poor emotional management and unhealthy work-life balance among nurses may produce several negative consequences for both healthcare workers and healthcare institutions. Emotionally exhausted nurses are more likely to experience burnout, reduced job satisfaction, psychological distress, decreased concentration, and interpersonal conflict within the workplace. Poor work-life balance may also contribute to absenteeism, low morale, declining productivity, strained family

relationships, and reduced quality of patient care. In healthcare environments where nurses constantly function under emotional pressure without adequate coping capacity, the possibility of medical errors, poor communication, and compromised patient outcomes may increase.

Despite growing research attention on occupational stress and coping strategies among nurses in Nigeria, limited empirical studies have specifically examined how emotional intelligence relates to work-life balance among nurses, particularly within tertiary healthcare institutions in Osun State. Most previous studies focused mainly on stress prevalence, burnout, job performance, or quality of life without adequately exploring whether emotional intelligence serves as a significant factor in helping nurses maintain work-life balance in demanding clinical environments. It is this identified gap that the present study seeks to fill by investigating emotional intelligence and work-life balance among nurses of Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determined:

1. The level of emotional intelligence among nurses of Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital
2. The level of work-life balance among nurses of Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital.
3. How emotional intelligence predict work-life balance among nurses of Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of emotional intelligence among nurses working at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of work-life balance among nurses working at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria?
3. To what extent does emotional intelligence predict work-life balance among nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

1. Emotional intelligence did not significantly predict work-life balance among nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive correlational survey research design. It is best suited to describe the level of emotional intelligence and work-life balance among nurses while simultaneously determining the predictive relationship between emotional intelligence and work-life balance. The target population for this study comprised 250 senior nursing personnel, including Directors of Nursing Services, Deputy and Assistant Directors, Chief and Assistant Nurse Tutors, and Principals of Nursing at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State. The hospital was purposively selected for the study because it has the largest concentration of the targeted population. A sample of 105

participants was drawn using simple random sampling technique.

Data for this study were collected through a structured questionnaire. The instrument consisted of three sections: Section A elicited demographic information of the respondents, Section B contained standardized items adapted from the Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS) to assess the level of emotional intelligence, while Section C adopted the Work-Life Balance Scale by Hayman (2005) to measure work-life balance among the nurses. The questionnaire was self-administered with the assistance of trained research assistants to the 105 randomly selected senior nursing personnel at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo. The

data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics in line with the three research questions. Research Questions 1 and 2 were answered using descriptive statistics such as mean scores, and standard deviation. Research Question 3 was analyzed using inferential statistics of regression analysis. All hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of emotional intelligence among nurses working at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Respondents' ratings on the level of emotional intelligence among nurses working at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital

S/N	Item statement	X	SD	Remarks
1	I am able to recognise when I am feeling stressed or overwhelmed while on duty.	3.81	0.45	Very high
2	I remain calm and composed when dealing with difficult patients or their relatives.	3.62	0.58	High
3	I can easily understand how my colleagues are feeling without them telling me directly	3.54	0.61	High
4	When I make a mistake at work, I acknowledge it rather than blaming others.	3.71	0.52	Very high
5	I am able to control my emotions even when I am criticised by a senior colleague or a patient.	3.68	0.49	High
6	I can sense when a patient is anxious or afraid even before they say anything.	3.79	0.47	Very high
Cluster Mean		3.69		High

The results presented in Table 1 reveal that nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital demonstrated a

high level of emotional intelligence with a cluster mean score of 3.69. All the items scored above 3.50, indicating strong agreement among

the respondents. The highest mean scores were recorded on the ability to recognise personal stress ($M = 3.81$) and sensing patients' anxiety ($M = 3.79$). The standard deviation across the items ranged from 0.45 to 0.61 with a cluster SD of 0.52. This relatively low standard deviation indicates a high level of consensus among the

respondents regarding their emotional intelligence capabilities.

Research Question 2: What is the level of work-life balance among nurses working at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Respondents' ratings on the level of work-life balance among nurses working at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital

S/N	Item statement	X	SD	Remarks
7	My work schedule allows me to attend important family events such as birthdays, weddings, or funerals.	2.68	0.71	Moderate
8	I am able to spend quality time with my children or other family members despite my work responsibilities.	2.74	0.68	Moderate
9	I often feel too exhausted from work to help with household chores or family tasks.	3.29	0.62	High
10	My family members understand and support the demands of my nursing job.	3.12	0.59	High
11	I am able to take adequate breaks and leave days without feeling guilty or worried about work.	2.81	0.74	Moderate
12	I feel that my nursing responsibilities interfere negatively with my personal relationships.	3.14	0.65	High
Cluster Mean		2.96		Moderate

The results in Table 2 indicate that nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital have a moderate level of work-life balance with a cluster mean score of 2.96. While respondents reported relatively good family understanding and support ($M = 3.12$), they experienced notable challenges in other areas. High mean scores on items 9 and 12 suggest that work-related exhaustion and negative interference with personal relationships remain significant issues. The

standard deviation scores ranged from 0.59 to 0.74; this moderate spread indicates a reasonable level of variation in the respondents' experiences of work-life balance.

Research Question 3 and Hypothesis 1
To what extent does emotional intelligence predict work-life balance among nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Simple regression on emotional intelligence predicting work-life balance among nurses

R	R square	Adjusted R square	Beta	df	Cal. t	P<0.05	Remark
0.776	0.602	0.602	0.776	103	9.732	0.000	Significant

Table 3 reveals a simple linear regression on the extent to which emotional intelligence predicts work-life balance among nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .776$) reveals that emotional intelligence is a strong positive predictor of work-life balance among nurses. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .602$) indicates that approximately 60.2% of the variance in work-life balance is explained by emotional intelligence.

The corresponding hypothesis revealed that emotional intelligence predicted work-life balance among nurses, $t(102) = 9.732, p < .05$. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that emotional intelligence significantly predicted work-life balance among nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

The finding of this study revealed that nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital demonstrated a high level of emotional intelligence. This finding aligns with several empirical studies conducted within and outside the healthcare sector. For instance, Oweidat, Alzoubi, Abu Shosha, Ta'an, Khalifeh,

and Al-Mugheed (2024) reported that nurses in Jordanian healthcare institutions exhibited high levels of emotional intelligence, particularly in emotional awareness, interpersonal communication, and emotional regulation. The study further explained that emotionally intelligent nurses were better able to manage stressful clinical situations while maintaining quality healthcare delivery. Similarly, Saikia, George, Unnikrishnan, Nayak, and Ravishankar (2024), in their scoping review on emotional intelligence among nurses, observed that emotional intelligence has increasingly become a strong psychological resource that improves nurses' mental health, communication skills, and workplace adjustment. In support of the present finding, Akinwale et al. (2024) also noted that nurses in Osogbo maintained positive caring behaviours despite stressful working conditions, implying the presence of strong emotional coping capacity among many nurses. However, this finding contrasts with the position of Omotoye, Olonade, Olaniyan, and Olusesi (2025), who found that workplace incivility and emotional exhaustion among healthcare workers in Osogbo negatively affected adaptive performance, suggesting that some nurses may still struggle with emotional regulation under prolonged workplace pressure. The variation may be linked to differences in institutional support, workload intensity, and

coping mechanisms available across healthcare facilities.

The study also revealed that nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital had a moderate level of work-life balance. This finding is consistent with previous empirical evidence indicating that nurses often experience difficulty maintaining a perfect balance between professional responsibilities and personal life demands due to the demanding nature of healthcare work. Auta (2024), in a study conducted among nurses in selected hospitals in Niger State during the COVID-19 pandemic, found that nurses demonstrated a moderate level of work-life balance characterized by moderate emotional exhaustion and depersonalization. The study explained that although nurses attempted to cope effectively with job demands, workplace stress and long working hours continued to affect their social and personal lives. In another related study, Okorie (2024) reported that poor work-life balance among nurses in Rivers State negatively affected job satisfaction and organizational productivity, largely due to increasing healthcare demands and insufficient workforce support. Similarly, Ngozi (2024) observed that nurses in both public and private hospitals in Makurdi experienced moderate work-life conditions because of irregular shifts, work overload, and family-role conflict. Nevertheless, the present finding differs slightly from the findings of Alkorashy, Basheer, and Mohamed (2024), who reported a relatively improved quality of work life among nurses with strong emotional support systems and organizational preparedness. This difference

may be attributed to variations in healthcare infrastructure, management practices, and institutional welfare policies across countries and healthcare settings.

Furthermore, the finding of this study revealed that emotional intelligence was a strong positive predictor of work-life balance among nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State. This finding is strongly supported by existing literature which suggests that emotionally intelligent nurses are better equipped to manage occupational stress, regulate emotions, and maintain healthier boundaries between work and personal life. Kumari and Raghuramapatruni (2024) found that emotional intelligence had a significant positive influence on nurses' ability to maintain work-life balance in private hospitals. The authors explained that nurses with higher emotional intelligence demonstrated stronger coping strategies, emotional stability, and resilience when dealing with workplace pressures. Likewise, Alkorashy et al. (2024) established that emotional intelligence significantly improved nurses' quality of work life by helping them manage emotional challenges associated with healthcare delivery during and after the COVID-19 period. Supporting this position, Zhang, Wu, Yang, Song, and Shen (2025) reported that emotional intelligence mediated the relationship between workplace stress and reflective ability among junior nurses, indicating that emotionally intelligent nurses are more capable of adapting positively under stressful conditions. In contrast, Roberts, Oladepo, Olapegba, and Uye (2024) argued that work-family conflict and job

stress were stronger predictors of quality of work-life among nurses than individual emotional factors alone.

Conclusion

This study examined emotional intelligence and work-life balance among nurses at Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. The findings established that nurses in the hospital demonstrated a high level of emotional intelligence, indicating that many of them possess the emotional awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and interpersonal skills required to function effectively within demanding clinical environments. Despite the emotionally challenging nature of nursing practice, the nurses appeared capable of managing workplace emotions and maintaining professional relationships that support healthcare delivery. The study further revealed that nurses experienced a moderate level of work-life balance. This suggests that although the nurses were making efforts to balance professional duties with personal and family responsibilities, existing workplace pressures such as workload, shift schedules, and emotional demands still posed challenges to achieving a healthier integration between work and personal life. Most importantly, the study established that emotional intelligence significantly and positively predicted work-life balance among nurses.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

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1. Hospital management should sustain and further strengthen emotional intelligence competencies among nurses through regular professional development programmes, emotional wellness workshops, communication training, and stress-management seminars.
2. The management of Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital should introduce policies that promote healthier work conditions for nurses. Such measures may include flexible shift scheduling, adequate staffing, provision of psychological support services, periodic leave opportunities, and reduction of excessive workload.
3. Hospital administrators and nursing leaders should integrate emotional intelligence development into staff orientation, leadership training, and workforce management strategies. Emotional intelligence assessment and training should also be incorporated into nursing development programmes to enhance nurses' coping abilities, interpersonal relationships, and emotional regulation skills within the workplace.
4. The government and relevant healthcare agencies should provide institutional support aimed at improving nurses' welfare and psychological well-being in tertiary healthcare institutions. This can be achieved through improved healthcare funding, recruitment of additional nursing personnel, and implementation of employee assistance programmes that support mental health and work-life integration among nurses.

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